

1 **GREB1 is activated in the BRCA1-deficient breast.**

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8 Citations

9 1. Gadad, S.S., Camacho, C.V., Malladi, V., Hutti, C.R., Nagari, A. and Kraus, W.L., 2021. PARP-1
10 regulates estrogen-dependent gene expression in estrogen receptor α -positive breast cancer cells.
11 Molecular Cancer Research, 19(10), pp.1688-1698.

12 2. Gorrini, C., Gang, B.P., Bassi, C., Wakeham, A., Baniyadi, S.P., Hao, Z., Li, W.Y., Cescon, D.W.,
13 Li, Y.T., Molyneux, S. and Penrod, N., 2014. Estrogen controls the survival of BRCA1-deficient cells via a
14 PI3K-NRF2-regulated pathway. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, 111(12),
15 pp.4472-4477.
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